

THE IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF NORMAT IN NAZAR ESHONQUL'S STORY "MEN OF WAR"

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ABSTRACT

In this article, one of the leading writers of today's literature, Nazar Eshanqul, talks about some important characteristics and signs of the character of the main character Normat in the short story "People of War".

INTRODUCTION

On the threshold of the independence period, great authors and important works appeared in our literature. One of such authors and such works is, of course, Nazar Eshanqul and his story "People of War".

In this story, the writer tries to reveal how great problems the war brought to people's lives and the era of it through the small village of Tersota and the characters living in it tried.

This article is about the lines related to the character of Normat in the story. Before we talk about the character of Normat in the story "Men of War", let's talk about what our scholars say about the character:

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

One of our famous literary experts, T. Boboev, while discussing character in his scientific views, makes the following points: "Character is a certain type of social activity. Character, as L. I. Timofeev said, is the core of an image. Character, first of all, a clear image of a person, manifested by his individual behavior and mental experiences in a concrete life situation. In general, the set of main signs that determine the important characteristics of a hero is called a character."

So, we can understand the scientist's thoughts as follows. In the socio-historical conditions, he was able to summarize the important characteristics of the people of his time

only an image can rise to the level of a character. In revealing the character of the hero of the work, not only his actions, but also the changes in his psyche play an important role. Continuing the above thoughts, the scientist approaches from different angles to explain the essence of his thoughts. "Theoretical literature shows two main features that determine the nature of character: a) character is determined by what shows the direction of a person's will. According to N. Pogodin, "if a person holds his nose, walks slowly or quickly, then it is not a character. "character is the emergence and expression of the will of a person in action", that is, the character is determined first of all by the will of a person, the direction of that will, its

emergence and expression. (M. Koshjanov). active attitude to the person and, on the contrary, arises from the attitude of the person to the environment; b) individual mental traits that determine behavior: courage, cowardice, honesty, dishonesty, initiative, hard work, apathy, laziness, etc. Describing a character without such individual mental traits will not". It seems that the scientist, relying on theoretical literature, shows two main features in determining the essence of character. The first of them is the direction of a person's will, and the second is the individual mental signs that determine behavior. So, if we see the character of the character in the character of the person's will, we can understand his inner world through the individual mental signs. The dynamics of the personality is fully manifested in the image of Normat. Although Normat is described as a quiet, polite person who does not hurt anyone at the beginning of the play, it is clear that he is ready to sacrifice his life for his honor, to give his word to others. It can be learned from the events of the play that he is a person who does not eat.

While working in his field, he got into an argument with the chairman Mirzaqul and nearly killed him with a sickle, he hid from his fellow villagers due to his wife's infidelity, his response to Mirzaqul's insults when Kholmat caught the sniper, and in general, he put his honor first. reveals more clearly. As you read the work, you will begin to notice changes in Normat's character, so how did all this happen?

What was the reason for this? What was all this change about? The main factor that changed Normat's character was the war. He turned into a completely different person from a serious, shy person who was confident, brave, who put his feelings of honor first. Through the image of Normat, the writer draws the changes that took place in the appearance and mentality of the people of that time, that is, the soldiers, against the general background: Oktam Normat, who has never fought in his life, but is nicknamed "wrestler" because of his big bones, is one of the leading horsemen of the village. His fellow villagers saw a living witness of the war they had heard about, with wrinkles appearing on his neck veins, scars on his neck, the stench of drugs still lingering, his appearance as old as fifty, his hair beginning to turn gray. they couldn't get used to the sneer on his face, his neck, which was gray behind his burnt ears, and his head, which was often shaking.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

But one thing should be noted, although the writer describes a person who was injured due to physical injuries by his fellow villagers, but he instilled hope and a sense of life in the character who returned from the war to such an extent that it is impossible not to be surprised. The main character of the work, Normat, was thirsty for a peaceful life, work, all nature, and love. We can read his situation in these lines: "He felt that everything in the world was created for his happiness and joy, and now I will not exchange these things for anything, even if God comes: He thought that these are dearer than my life, they gave me life. He opened the windows of his heart to the life that is coming alive.

The writer describes how a person returning from war enters a peaceful life with new hopes and a sense of unlimited vitality through the changes that occurred during Normat's return from the war. After a while, Normat can't get rid of the scars left by the war. gives his repeated collisions with pain: the situation that occurred when Holmat went to catch the sniper (Normat the wrestler with bulging veins in the temple, bruises around the eyes, yellow

foam at one end of the mouth was appearing. Normat screamed, grabbed the veins of his temple with both hands and fell back to the ground spinning) and his last state due to the betrayal of his wife Anzirat (Normat went crazy both in his appearance and in his actions. His eyes his cups were enlarged, his face was darkening, his eyes were filled with blood) he draws in a completely opposite way to the above situation.

In fact, it was this terrible war that caused innocent children to become orphans, the lamentations of parents who lost their children, and various betrayals. The war spared no one. Even if he wanted to wash away his blood through work, the war did not allow him to do so. He himself remembers what his father once said to him: "Wherever human blood is shed, kindness and blessing will arise. He who eats the bread of that land will become a bloodthirsty, my poor father used to say. After living a prophetic life "The man left without killing. Even when they robbed his house, he did not take a rifle. Whoever holds a rifle in his hand is a man of war, and that man himself will be killed by war," he said.

In fact, Normat was a person who entered the war holding a rifle and lost many people's blood. Even though he returned from the war healthy and lives thousands of kilometers away from it, the war managed to spread its cold breath to these places. his injuries did not end and caused a tragic fate for a family.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the writer was able to reveal that the war leaves scars on people's hearts and causes huge tragedies in the case of Normat.

Since the beginning of the story, the character of Normat has changed several times. At the beginning of the play, he appeared in a humble and dignified manner, but in the middle of the work, he appeared in a somewhat depressed and rude manner.

Normat fought with himself until the end of the play, on the one hand, his sense of honor tormented him, on the other hand, his love for his children prevailed. his problem seemed insignificant compared to that of Mallaboy, he tried to forgive his wife Anzirat, but he could not bear another betrayal, he shot Mirzaqul and his wife and committed suicide. A family became a hazan. The author revealed that there are many such families on the example of the small village of Tersota and the fate of Normat.

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